

TREAT-AD

TaRget Enablement to Accelerate
Therapy Development for AD

TICAM1

(TIR domain containing adaptor molecule 1)

A Target Enabling Package (TEP)

Gene ID / UniProt ID / EC	148022 / Q8IUC6
Target Nominator	TREAT-AD
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Therapeutic Area(s)	Alzheimer's disease
Document version	1.0
Document version date	May 2024
Citation	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14594978
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CONTENTS OF TEP

Bioinformatic analysis: Target source & hypothesis

Protein constructs & expression methods: plasmids for human TICAM1 protein expression in mammalian cells

TARGET SOURCE & HYPOTHESIS

Why was the target selected? This target was identified through a gene set enrichment analysis (GSEA) of the TREAT-AD target risk scores. The gene is among the leading edge (i.e. top-scoring) genes from the significantly enriched "Innate Immune Response" GO term. Network pathway modeling along with patient pseudotime analysis also implicated this gene as a central node within the network and a protein whose expression changes in pseudotemporally early disease progression.

TREAT-AD Target Risk Score: 2.4 (rank #8557, 65.7th percentile)

The TREAT-AD Center has developed a target ranking score encompassing genomics and genetics evidence. The Target Risk Score represents the gene target’s general relevance to Alzheimer’s Disease, and is the sum of the target’s Genetics Score and Genomics Score. Target Risk Score values range from 0 to 5, with 5 being evidence of the strongest association with AD. A complete description of the methodology used to calculate these scores is available [here](#). This score was taken from Agora, Data Version syn13363290-v62.

The TREAT-AD Target Risk Score for this target is 2.4 out of 5 (rank #8557, 65.7th percentile). The individual score components include 1.89 of 3 for genetics, and 0.51 out of 2 for genomics. The meta-analysis of proteomic and transcriptomic data sources used in the genomics score indicates that the expression of TICAM1 RNA is significantly increased in brains from patients with AD.

The TREAT-AD Center has also developed a target categorization system specific to AD relevant processes, termed biological domains (biodomains). These biological domains are defined by constituent Gene Ontology (GO) terms and genes are then annotated to specific biological domains via GO term annotations. TICAM1 is annotated to GO terms from 6 biodomains, primarily to terms from the Immune Response, Apoptosis, Endolysosome, Lipid Metabolism, and Autophagy domains.

Overall	rank	pctl	GeneticsScore	OmicsScore
2.396	8557	65.72	1.889	0.5069

Cell-type specific expression is assessed using single-cell expression data from the Seattle Alzheimer’s Disease Brain Cell Atlas (SEA-AD). The distribution of expression values for all genes found in each broad cell type are displayed as violins. The expression of the target in subtypes within each broad class is shown as a point. Blue points show the summary expression of cells from individuals with no dementia, while red points show summary metrics of cells from dementia patients. Open circles reflect low confidence measures of

expression. The expression of TICAM1 is not confidently detected in any cell types within this dataset.

SUMMARY OF PROJECT

TICAM1 is a key adaptor protein connecting activated toll-like receptors (TLRs) 3 and 4 to the type 1 interferon response as part of the innate immune system’s response to pathogens or damaged tissues.

TICAM1 is centered in a large network of interacting proteins responsible for this response and has many binding partners. As activation of the innate immune response is emerging as a vital contributor to the pathology of Alzheimer's disease (AD), study of TICAM1 may help increase our understanding of the AD disease process and ultimately aid in the creation of treatment options for AD. This TEP focuses on the development of research tools necessary for studying TICAM1 and its role in AD pathology.

SCIENTIFIC BACKGROUND

TIR domain-containing adaptor molecule 1 (TICAM1), also known as Toll-interleukin-1 receptor (TIR)-domain-containing adaptor-inducing IFN- β (TRIF), is a key adaptor protein in the innate immune response. TICAM1 is expressed at a low level diffusely throughout the cytoplasm in most cell types but colocalizes with downstream signaling molecules in speckle-like structures when activated [1-3]. TICAM1 bridges activated Toll-like receptors (TLRs), which recognize pathogen associated molecular patterns (PAMPs) and damaged-associated molecular patterns (DAMPs), to downstream activation of the type 1 interferon (IFN) response[3, 4]. TICAM1 is recruited to endosomal membranes for signaling by intracellular TLRs 3 and 4 when activated by respective ligands such as double-stranded RNA (dsRNA) or lipopolysaccharide (LPS)[5-7]. TICAM1 then recruits a network of other binding partners and signaling molecules, including TRAF3, TRAF6, TBK1, IKK- ϵ , RIP-1, NAP1, and/or TAK1, culminating in the activation and nuclear translocation of transcription factors including IRF3, IRF7, NF- κ B, and AP-1[2, 5]. Activation of these transcription factors results in the production of type I IFNs, proinflammatory cytokines, and chemokines as part of a critical response to pathogens but also plays a key role in autoimmunity and thus is implicated in inflammatory conditions[2, 4, 8].

Facilitating TICAM1's interactions with other members of the innate immune response network are the protein's several functional regions. The first 153 amino acids of the 712 residue TICAM1 protein comprise the N-terminal protease-resistant domain which is involved in IRF3 activation[9]. Next the intermediate disordered proline-rich region from amino acids 154–392 contains binding sites for many downstream proteins including TBK1, TRAF2, and TRAF6[2, 10]. Amino acids 393 through 545 contain the TIR domain and are necessary for binding to TLR3[11]. Finally, the remaining C-terminal region contains an RIP homotypic interaction motif (RHIM) domain and is responsible for NF- κ B activation and apoptosis[12, 13]. Continued studies of the structure and function of TICAM1 domains are a promising field for determining regulation of the innate immune response.

Aberrant activation of the innate immune response is a key contributor to neurodegenerative diseases, including Alzheimer's disease, Parkinson's disease, amyotrophic lateral sclerosis, and frontotemporal dementia[8]. In cell and animals, modulation of TLR signaling, such as with those directly upstream of TICAM1, alters the pathological features of Alzheimer's disease including amyloid beta expression and cognition in mice[4, 8, 14]. Further study of TICAM1 can increase our understanding of the AD disease process and perhaps lead to expanded treatment modalities for AD.

RESULTS – THE TEP

Protein Constructs

1. pDEST26-hTICAM1-Nluc: a plasmid suitable for expression of full length, human TICAM1 with a C-terminal NanoLuciferase tag. [Addgene Plasmid #197634](#).
2. pCDNA3-hTICAM1-VenusFlag: a plasmid suitable for expression of full length, human TICAM1 with a C-terminal VenusFlag tag. [Addgene Plasmid #197632](#).

3. pcDNA3-VenusFlag-hTICAM1: a plasmid suitable for expression of full length, human TICAM1 with a N-terminal VenusFlag tag. [Addgene Plasmid #197631](#).

See **Additional information (section 1)** with details of plasmid expression constructs and purification procedures.

CONCLUSION

The tools presented here provide a foundation for further investigation of the role of TICAM1 in AD.

FUNDING INFORMATION

The work performed by the Emory-Sage-SGC TREAT-AD Center has been funded by the National Institute on Aging through grant U54 AG065187.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Materials and Methods

Proteins Constructs

All relevant plasmids are available on addgene: [TREAT-AD plasmid collection](#)

References

1. Funami, K., et al., *Spatiotemporal mobilization of Toll/IL-1 receptor domain-containing adaptor molecule-1 in response to dsRNA*. J Immunol, 2007. **179**(10): p. 6867-72.
2. Chen, Y., et al., *Toll-like receptor 3 (TLR3) regulation mechanisms and roles in antiviral innate immune responses*. J Zhejiang Univ Sci B, 2021. **22**(8): p. 609-632.
3. Ullah, M.O., et al., *TRIF-dependent TLR signaling, its functions in host defense and inflammation, and its potential as a therapeutic target*. J Leukoc Biol, 2016. **100**(1): p. 27-45.
4. Federico, S., et al., *Modulation of the Innate Immune Response by Targeting Toll-like Receptors: A Perspective on Their Agonists and Antagonists*. J Med Chem, 2020. **63**(22): p. 13466-13513.
5. Luo, L., et al., *Signalling, sorting and scaffolding adaptors for Toll-like receptors*. J Cell Sci, 2019. **133**(5).
6. Matsumoto, M., et al., *Toll-IL-1-receptor-containing adaptor molecule-1: a signaling adaptor linking innate immunity to adaptive immunity*. Prog Mol Biol Transl Sci, 2013. **117**: p. 487-510.
7. Yamamoto, M., et al., *Role of adaptor TRIF in the MyD88-independent toll-like receptor signaling pathway*. Science, 2003. **301**(5633): p. 640-3.
8. Castro-Gomez, S. and M.T. Heneka, *Innate immune activation in neurodegenerative diseases*. Immunity, 2024. **57**(4): p. 790-814.
9. Tatematsu, M., et al., *A molecular mechanism for Toll-IL-1 receptor domain-containing adaptor molecule-1-mediated IRF-3 activation*. J Biol Chem, 2010. **285**(26): p. 20128-36.
10. Sasai, M., et al., *Direct binding of TRAF2 and TRAF6 to TICAM-1/TRIF adaptor participates in activation of the Toll-like receptor 3/4 pathway*. Mol Immunol, 2010. **47**(6): p. 1283-91.
11. Patra, M.C., et al., *A Computational Probe into the Structure and Dynamics of the Full-Length Toll-Like Receptor 3 in a Phospholipid Bilayer*. Int J Mol Sci, 2020. **21**(8).

12. Kumeta, H., et al., *The N-terminal domain of TIR domain-containing adaptor molecule-1, TICAM-1*. J Biomol NMR, 2014. **58**(3): p. 227-30.
13. Mahita, J. and R. Sowdhamini, *Integrative modelling of TIR domain-containing adaptor molecule inducing interferon- β (TRIF) provides insights into its autoinhibited state*. Biol Direct, 2017. **12**(1): p. 9.
14. Liu, H.Y., C.Y. Chen, and Y.P. Hsueh, *Innate immune responses regulate morphogenesis and degeneration: roles of Toll-like receptors and Sarm1 in neurons*. Neurosci Bull, 2014. **30**(4): p. 645-54.

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